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Abstract: This article provides information about the impact of mass media on human and community life, as well as information attacks and ways to fight against them.

Key words: mass media, popular culture, internet, computer, computer network, web audience, social networks.

Nowadays, the world is changing rapidly. In all spheres, it is necessary to receive and deliver information, to form an effective public opinion. In such complex conditions, life puts new demands and tasks before us.

Mass media is the most basic, powerful and influential means of ideology. Because the mass media serves as a unique educator of the public, an organizer of important events, and an effective tool for solving current problems. It is through mass media that our national values and universal values, national ideals and democratic principles are promoted. Mass media have always been a unique measure and indicator of democracy and freedom of speech. Free and independent mass media stimulate and strengthen democratic development. Modern mass media, television, computer, Internet, mobile phone and other means are changing the nationality, thinking and worldview of people, especially young people. This is evident in the fact that developed countries, with the help of these tools, are making it their main strategic policy to standardize the consciousness, outlook and lifestyle of the peoples of the world and to inculcate the "mass culture" they are forming into.

The Internet has become an important part of today's information space. Currently, the Internet can be used not only through a computer network, but also through space communication satellites, radio signal, cable television, telephone, and cellular communication. The Internet is becoming an integral part of people's lives. The fact that today more than 2 billion people use it to one degree or another confirms the correctness of these opinions.

The fact that the Internet is becoming an integral part of people's lives can be seen from the following figures: from 2000 to the end of 2012, the number of Internet users in the world increased by 9.6 times to 2.4 billion people, and the number of mobile subscribers increased by 13.4 times to 6.7 amounted to a billion. 44.8% of Internet users (1.1 billion people) belong to Asia, 21.6% (519 million people) to Europe, 11.4% (274 million people) to North America. 45% of the world's web audience is under 25 years old. 68% of these teenagers send SMS messages to someone every day, 51% use social networks, and 30% use e-mail. At the moment, there are about 600 million websites in the virtual world, with an average of 201.4 trillion per month. video is viewed, 144 billion every day. an email will be sent.

The number of Internet users in Uzbekistan has increased by 22.1 million. The number of mobile Internet users is 19 million. The level of coverage of settlements with mobile communication was 97%, and mobile internet coverage was 87%. About 26,000 websites in the "Uz" domain are operating. More than 200 websites are registered as mass media. The influence of the Internet depends to a large extent on the speed of the materials provided, the relevance of the issues raised, and the level of analysis and effective solutions to the existing problems.

As our first president Islam Karimov noted, we should not forget that "today even a small message directed against human spirituality, which at first glance seems trivial, gains strength from the intensity of globalization in the world of information and has an invisible, but harmful effect. can cause irreparable damage".

Currently, according to experts, 49 percent of computer games distributed over the Internet have a significant appearance of violence and evil, and 41 percent of militant (based on various shootings and explosions) games have the hero of the game o He commits such violence and evil to achieve his goal. In 17 percent of games, this violence and evil is the main goal. The development of the Internet, the opportunities it provides, also creates a unique addiction. According to data, about 10 percent of Internet users around the world are firmly attached to it.

One of the big politicians, the former British Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher, said, "The mass media serves as oxygen for terrorists." A person who digests this sentence comes to the conclusion that "mass media is as necessary as air for terrorists." At first glance, this idea seems illogical. How about digging deeper? In fact, terrorists seek to instill fear and anger in millions by brutally killing a number of people. So their goal is not to kill, but to have a strong influence on the public. Unfortunately, some mass media unknowingly "serve" to increase the disruptive effect of terrorism. Their

alarming information about the consequences of terrorism intensifies people's fear, fear, and feeling of insecurity.

In order to destabilize the situation or to influence the decision-making by state bodies or to hinder political or other social activities, taking the life of a state or public figure or a representative of authority in connection with the state or public activities of a state or public figure or causing damage to his body, - shall be punished with confiscation of property and deprivation of liberty from ten to fifteen years. Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations". "Separation of religion from the state" Activities of religious organizations, trends, sects, etc., which support terrorism, drug business and organized crime, as well as pursue other malicious goals, are prohibited. Any attempt to put pressure on state authorities and administrative bodies, officials, as well as clandestine religious activities are prohibited by law. There is a need to organize counter-propaganda against such information. Currently, the changes in our life, the logic of our reforms require everyone to work in a new way, to come up with new ideas and initiatives. In this sense, strengthening the material and technical base of the mass media, personnel capacity, achieving a worthy place of our national press in the international arena, developing internet journalism, wide introduction of market mechanisms in publishing, book sales, subscription issues, establishing work in an environment of openness and healthy competition. we have to work hard on.

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